

An underwater scene with a network overlay. The background is a deep blue ocean with light rays filtering down. A white network of lines and dots is overlaid on the right side, suggesting a data network or connectivity.

Tracking the Pulse of the Ocean

BioGeoSea Consortium Response to the European Ocean Observation Initiative

This document has been produced within the BioGeoSea project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101216427. This document reflects the views of the BioGeoSea consortium only, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

The EU funded project BioGeoSea enhances biogeochemical Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs), integrates observing systems, advances data products, improves models, and develops ocean indicators. We deliver the knowledge and tools needed to protect the future of our blue planet by turning trusted data into insight that enables the development of solutions and guidelines for sustainable ocean management.

Processes such as ocean acidification, deoxygenation, and greenhouse gas fluxes drive profound changes in marine ecosystems. These dynamics can be observed through observations of EOVs and tracked with indicators – revealing how the ocean and our planet are changing, and as a tool to assess management efforts.

Sustained information on ocean biogeochemistry through sustained observations is important for society, the blue economy and for understanding the foundations of climate change impact, biodiversity shifts, and ocean health. Increasingly, forecast capability on these topics is becoming more relevant and needed. Observations of ocean biogeochemical variables are not isolated from observations of physics, biology and human impacts (including pollution), but should be integrated to a holistic and sustained ocean observing system.

Creating ocean information requires that a full value chain of ocean observing is operating. A main hurdle towards a sustained and efficient European Ocean Observing System is the fragmentation across Europe, i.e. many actors with different mandate and priorities, that are often funded through short-time projects, without long-term sustainability prospects.

The development and delivery of robust ocean indicators is a useful way of disseminating complex data in a robust, but easily understandable manner – Ocean indicators refer to metrics based on scientifically verified approaches and data that allow for the identification of the state in ocean phenomena across a range of temporal and spatial scales that are accessible to inform decision-makers and beyond.

It is important to foster science-industry collaboration, and to encourage the private sector to invest in ocean observation and to incentivize investment in new and accessible ocean observing technology. It is also important that access to ocean observations and information is open and available.

We therefor plea for:

1. A European Ocean Observing System that needs a systematic design for optimal integration between in-situ and remote sensing systems, considering impact and cost-efficiencies. The concept of Essential Ocean Variables should be considered as a cornerstone of system design. Ocean observing networks using similar technology and similar standard methodologies for executing the ocean observation activities should be strengthened and coordinated across Europe. Ocean observations should adhere to endorsed Best Practices for consistency and efficiency.
2. Establishing a forum between the European Commission and the member states that is needed to share information and coordination of activities. This forum needs to be successively strengthened to coordinate mandated actions and trigger collaboration between private and public entities. The forum should consider the whole value chain, from agreement on information needs and priorities to delivery of data and information, with a

focus on the observational aspects. In addition, it will be important to form a decision-making body of Member State representatives for targeted discussions on priorities and co-designing the observing system that supports societal needs in Europe while, at the same time, contributes to the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS). Such a forum should consider existing structures and could build on the European Ocean Observing System (EOOS).

The Initiative should explore a co-funded European Ocean Observing Facility model, similar to other European research infrastructures, where Member States commit baseline funding and the European Commission provides strategic top-up investment. Ocean observing infrastructure should be formally recognized as critical infrastructure for climate resilience and environmental security. To overcome the current fragmentation, the Initiative should establish a legally supported coordination mechanism that clearly defines Member State responsibilities for sustained in-situ observing contributions.

This mechanism should include multiannual national commitments to observe EOVs, with transparent reporting and accountability. Short-term project funding cannot substitute for structural, operational funding of long-term observing systems.

The Initiative should support the co-development and regular delivery of operational ocean indicators that are directly linked to European policy frameworks and biodiversity restoration targets. Indicators should be uncertainty-quantified and regularly updated through sustained observing systems.

We therefore recommend:

1. To define essential ocean products and services and providing incentives for the Member States to support the long-term/sustained data flow for those. Ocean observations should be treated as critical (research) infrastructure, and the initiative should incentivize Member States to join and support European-wide marine Research infrastructures. The European Ocean Observation Initiative should provide the sustained observational backbone required for the Digital Twin of the Ocean and other advanced modelling systems, ensuring that forecasting and scenario tools are grounded in in-situ and remote observations.
2. To establish a legal framework for ocean observations that is needed to enable a sustained ocean observation system, and for securing long-term funding schemes.
3. To set up a co-funding mechanism between Member States and the European Commission for global and pan-European in-situ ocean observing systems.
4. To develop clear mechanisms to incentivize private sector participation in ocean observations, including data-sharing partnerships, co-investment schemes, and procurement instruments. Industry actors benefiting from ocean information should be structurally integrated into governance discussions.

The Ocean Observation Initiative has the potential to shift ocean observation from a fragmented niche activity to a norm, providing the citizens and industry in Europe with the ocean information needed for climate adaptation, sustaining biodiversity, and supporting a rapidly growing blue economy.